

Prevalence of Renal Disease in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

A leading cause of death and disability globally, chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a serious public health concern. One of the world's most densely inhabited country is Bangladesh. Renal disorders are becoming more widely known and account for a sizable portion of the healthcare industry. There are over 20 million people with chronic kidney disease, and each year, 35,000 to 40,000 of them reach end stage renal disease. Diabetes mellitus, chronic glomerulonephritis, and hypertension are the main factors contributing to chronic kidney disease. Dialysis or kidney transplants are available as therapies for renal failure. Acute renal damage, kidney cysts, kidney stones, and kidney infections are a few other kidney issues. Acute kidney injury is frequently caused by hypovolemia, sepsis, obstetric problems, and medications (including herbal and homoeopathic therapies). Only 25% of patients with end-stage renal illness have access to treatment in Bangladesh, despite the country performing all three forms of renal replacement therapy (hemodialysis, peritoneal dialysis, and kidney transplantation). This is because of poor facilities and excessive healthcare expenses. Opportunities for research and teaching are growing in conjunction with international organizations. Although the country's renal services seem up to current, they need constant improvement to handle the growing strain. In order to control and lower the high risk of impairment related to CKD, public health policymakers and the government need to pay it greater attention.

Keywords: CKD, transplantation, mortality

Introduction:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD), which can lead to renal failure, cardiovascular disease, and early death, is regarded as one of the biggest public health issues in the world [1]. According to the Global Burden of Disease Study (GBDS) report from 2010, CKD was the world's 18th leading cause of mortality, up from 27th in 1990 [2]. Approximately 500 million people globally suffer from CKD [3,4], and the burden is particularly severe in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa [5]. Bangladesh, a heavily populated developing country in the Southeast, is seeing an increase in the annual prevalence of CKD. Bangladesh was included in a global analysis of six regions that assessed the prevalence of CKD to be 14% [6]. A study done in the city of Dhaka among individuals over the age of 30 revealed a prevalence of CKD of 26% [7], while a study done among urban Dhaka inhabitants over the age of 15 reported a prevalence of 13% [8]. The documented differences in CKD prevalence among Bangladeshi communities, however, may be attributable to a number of variables, including the design of a cross-sectional study employing sample size, study time, and the geographic locations of urban and rural settings. According to a study, the prevalence of CKD varies by age group, between men and women, and by socioeconomic status, as well as by place [6]. In one study, the mortality rate was 18.5%, and 8.1% of all hospitalized patients had AKI. In the same study, 14.4% of the 3764 ICU patients had AKI, and 17.2% of those patients passed away [9]. Bangladesh has higher rates of chronic kidney disease (CKD) than the rest of the world and even South Asia. This information causes alarm and compels us to pay attention. It becomes crucial that public health policymakers and government representatives intervene and tackle this pressing problem. The emphasis must shift to reducing the high risk of CKD-related disability in order to protect our population's health and well-being.

Kidney disease- Bangladesh scenario:

Because we lack a national registry, a reporting system, regional disparities, and regular national and regional surveys, we have a limited understanding of the prevalence of AKI. In the treating institutions, there are variations in case management protocols and definitions. There is almost no referral culture, and the majority of cases have delayed referrals that have bad outcomes. Less than 25% of cases of acute kidney injury are caused by obstetrical or surgical issues, with medical issues accounting for the majority of cases. 63% of the causes were pre-renal, 19% were renal, and 18% were post-renal. Pre-renal AKI's most frequent cause was post-diarrheal hypovolemia, while glomerulonephritis is one of its renal causes [9]. AKI caused by sepsis has recently become a significant problem in the care of critically ill patients [10]. According to a 2012 investigation into community-based prevalence statistics, one-third of rural Bangladeshis were at risk of having undetected chronic kidney disease [11]. The fact that CKD prevalence varies among age groups, genders, socioeconomic circumstances, and geographic areas is noted. End-Stage Renal Disease (ESRD), which requires resource-intensive management like dialysis and kidney transplantation, is more likely to develop in those with CKD.

Fig 1. Causes of CKD (source: Bangladesh renal journal)

CKD prevalence as determined by the GFR equation:

So many studies were carried out in Bangladesh to determine various type and percentage of chronic kidney diseases. The MDRD (modification of diet in renal disease) equation was applied in eight investigations, and the prevalence of CKD was 7.2% [12], 19.5% [11], 13.1% [13], 66.4% [14], 12.8% [8], 13.9% [15], 63.5% [16], and 22.9% [17]. In four investigations that employed the CG to estimate the GFR, the prevalence was 9.9% [12], 19% [11], 16% [13], and 64.7% [16]. The CG group's pooled prevalence was lower (20.13%) than that of the MDRD (22.78%) and CKD-EPI (22.65%) groups. The smallest sample size was 125 [14], and the biggest was 218,888 [17].

Renal transplantation in Bangladesh:

The first successful kidney transplant from a donor performed in Bangladesh in 1982, marking a crucial turning point for the nation. Since then, there have been more than 2,300 kidney transplants, signaling a significant progress in renal care. With seven successful cases in 2018, the introduction of ABO-incompatible kidney transplantation increased the possibilities in this area[18]. Despite these successes, obstacles still stand in the way of both living and deceased donor transplantation. Due to potential donors' lack of knowledge and fear of giving, a scarcity of living donors continues to be a major barrier. Additionally, the exorbitant expense of tests, procedures, and immunosuppressive medications, along with the lack of government funding, make transplantation prohibitive for a lot of individuals. Inadequate laboratory facilities and a lack of trained transplant doctors, surgeons, and nurses also provide substantial obstacles to the successful completion of transplant surgeries. To improve transplant services and give patients with end-stage renal disease (ESRD) better treatment, these problems must be resolved. Numerous obstacles prevent the deployment of transplants from

deceased donors. Critically important is the shortage of intensive care unit (ICU) infrastructure for detecting, declaring, and maintaining brain-dead donors. Organ procurement and brain death committees, among other specialized committees, have been established to help with deceased donor transplantation. To offer adequate support and care for both donors and recipients, training programs for transplant coordinators and grief counsellors have been started.

Renal care in Bangladeshi private institution:

The government of Bangladesh is gradually improving nephrology treatment throughout the nation through state hospitals and institutions, but the majority of kidney care, including dialysis and transplantation, is now delivered by private nongovernmental organizations (NGO) and corporate hospitals. These corporate hospitals offer all forms of renal care, but they are out of the reach of the majority of the people. Various NGOs provide cheap services to the disadvantaged citizens. The Kidney Foundation of Bangladesh is a nonprofit company that offers low-cost renal treatment and is committed to providing top-notch services for kidney-related problems all around the country. Their initiatives cover a broad range of activities, such as providing comprehensive medical care, such as dialysis and transplantation services, running public education campaigns, advancing kidney health research, training medical professionals, promoting policy changes, connecting with communities through outreach initiatives, and working with international partners. The foundation works to prevent kidney disorders, boost treatment outcomes, and improve overall quality of life for people in Bangladesh who are affected by kidney-related health issues through these several projects. Other tiny non-profit organizations work to provide kidney treatment, particularly dialysis, to the nation's underprivileged citizens.

Training in nephrology in Bangladesh:

Two course options are available in Bangladesh for postgraduate nephrology training: MD (Nephrology) and FCPS (Nephrology). MD (Nephrology): Starting in 2009, practical training has been a feature of MD residency courses. Only non-residency MD courses were offered before to that. Many institutions, including BSMMU, Dhaka Medical College, the National Institute of Kidney Disease and Urology (NIKDU), and others currently provide exclusively MD residency programs. Phase A of these programs lasts for two years in several medical specialties, while Phase B lasts three years for advanced nephrology training. Training in renal transplantation and thesis work are both covered.

FCPS (Nephrology): Following successful completion of FCPS Nephrology Part One, students complete two years of medical school before sitting for the FCPS midterm. Then, three years of advanced nephrology training that is approved by BCPS and takes place in different hospitals follows. While kidney transplants are only performed at a few institutions, dialysis and CAPD procedures are offered in many. Nowadays, more than 300 nephrologists are dispersed throughout Bangladesh, offering their knowledge in each district. In addition to performing crucial operations including kidney biopsy, vascular catheterization, intermittent peritoneal dialysis (IPD), and continuous ambulatory peritoneal dialysis (CAPD), their services also include the treatment of a variety of renal illnesses.

Concluding remarks:

Bangladeshis have a greater prevalence of CKD than those in South Asian countries. The significant risk of disability due to CKD must be controlled and reduced, which is why it is crucial for key public health policymakers and the government to take action. The burden of nephrology in Bangladesh is enormous, and the resources available are insufficient. The various renal care approaches are upgraded daily. Bangladesh is not falling behind as a growing country, but it does require more qualified personnel and resources to keep up. The significant risk of impairment associated with CKD needs to be controlled and reduced, thus public health policymakers and the government need to pay it more attention.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

There is no conflict of interest regarding this paper.

Availability of data and materials

The data and materials used to support the findings of this study are publicly available.

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